

Not Profit Technologies: Emphasizing Open Source Cloud Computing

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Abstract

Not Profit Technologies is an important aspect these days and mainly dedicated to the building and designing of technologies and products which are mainly used for the community or society or other public or organization. Virtually, it comprises IT and ECE system which supports the goal of nonprofit, nongovernment, grassroots and so many dedicated organizations. Not Profit Technologies may be software technology, communication technology, multimedia technology, networking technology, and any other technologies which are mainly used for the community or any purposes. However, some tools and technologies are created mainly for the use of nonprofit organizations. This paper talks about the Not Profit Technologies including its inner meaning and characteristics and speedily open source cloud platform in a brief manner.

Keywords

Technologies, Cloud Computing, Open Source Software, FOSS, NGO, Non-Profit Technologies, Community Science, Computing, Computing, Open Source,

Introduction

Non Profit organizations basically use so many electronic goods and technologies such as computer, internet, and intranet for several official activities and to communicate other organizations and units with electronic means [1- 2]. There is a close relationship between Non profit technologies and Non profit organization as in many cases, it is applicable such as volunteer management, donor management, project management, human and financial programming and so on. Not Profit Technologies played an important role and as of now, around 30 software applications are prepared for several non profit organization activities

which are mentioned above. Apart from software and packages of database, networking, communication, multimedia, non profit technologies are also recently deployed in some recent areas [3-4].

Objective

The main aim and objective of this paper include but not limited to as follows—

- To know basic about Not Profit Technologies and computing in a brief manner;
- To learn about the advantage, benefits, and features of the Not Profit Technologies in a simple manner;
- To learn about the open source software as well as operating system as Not Profit Technologies;
- To know about the Usability Engineering, Human Computer Interaction and other technologies with Not Profit Technological point of view;
- To learn about the Cloud Computing as a Not Profit Technologies.

Not Profit Technologies

Not Profit Technologies is actually a concept and procedure in which is mainly planning and implemented for design and development of tools and products which are mainly available free of cost.

Fig: 1- Main Facet of Social Software Engineering Practices

In software world, there are so many application and packages are available in so many application and packages are available in so many platform and for several activities [5 -6]. In communication sector so many E-Mail system are developed and these are free for common uses such as Gmail, Rediffmail, Hotmail, and so on.

In business sector, office packages with data processing and spreadsheet and other are available such King Soft, Linux Office packages and so on. These are useful in several

official activities. As far as operating system is concerned, there are so many available packages such as Android OS, Linux OS, Unix OS and so on [7-8].

Not Profit Technologies mostly are open source based and here user can see and modify the code and may prepare the software depending upon need. This is idle for small organization and NGO as purchasing new software, application, packages, and hardware as cost dependent. And more than this in Not Profit Technologies no need to take initiative for the maintenance. Future maintenance services are available with huge volunteer and service provider world wide and thus such technologies are up to date many ways.

Fig: 2- Basic Application domain of Non Profit Technologies

Recently apart from NGO and small organization big organization, corporate houses using so many Not Profit Technologies such as Facebook, Orkut, Twitter, and other wikis. Here one can share and communicate text, audio, and video with out any direct investment for software and facilities and these technologies are equally important in all most all type of organization, irrespective of profit making or non profit or home uses [9-10]. YouTube, WhatsApps, are another important name in this regard. Which change the traditional communication system radically and popular in all domains such as business, wikis, are another important name of Not Profit Technologies dedicated to modernization and scientific, casual, and professional communication.

In educational system too, Not Profit Technologies is valuable as with social networking, you-tube based system promote campus based learning and online and e-learning system. Hence many ways, Not Profit Technologies is improving computer literacy and uses among the people and small organization apart from big concerned.

Open Source Software and Cloud Computing

Open Source Software are available with open code and programming and here one can see, change, modify and implementing depending upon need. Open Technology, Open standard and framework are the main mantra of open source software. Initially, the movement towards open and free software and application started during the last of 1990's. And there after so many new application and software are evolved on various fields such as office practice, multimedia, database, operating system and so on [11 -12].

Fig: 3- Cloud Computing and its application with platform

As in profit making organization, they can adopt their own IT staff for implementation and future management; but non profit making organization currently able to take their own staff and hence the services may be avail by the online support [10-11].

Cloud Computing is actually a type of IT and Computing platform which is mainly dedicated to virtualization of hardware, software, application, utilities and other from the remote place. And in such technology are centralize unit or system may run or handle so many clients at a time. This platform is called Public Cloud. This may be treated as partial Not Profit Technologies as within an interaction based connection one can get wider services with the help of central processing unit. Hence, there is no need of own IT and hardware. However, depending upon need and security, one can use. Separately build own cloud unit and that is called private cloud computing [1, 10].

However, Cloud Computing recently comes as Not Profit Technologies with the help of implementation of open standard and technologies to the existing feature and facilities. Recently tendency towards open source cloud computing is rising, in this platform free and open source cloud based services are available by some of the service providers. And in this

case, one can save data and storage 250 GB to beyond. In this technology, a concerned organization can get registered by the internet and may save and store data without own hardware, database, or hardware disk and so on. Virtually, Open Technology based clouds are in the beginning stage and in near future, it will dominate private as well as public cloud many cases [2, 6]. There are so many O/S are comes with Cloud Computing platform and among them, some popular are listed in figure 4.

Cloud Enable FOSS software
<i>GLIDE</i>
<i>KOHIVE</i>
<i>GLOUDU</i>
<i>MY GOYA</i>
<i>ZIMDESK</i>
<i>GS</i>

Fig: 4- Some popular and Free Cloud Computing software

Findings

- Not Profit Technologies are very much popular in Social Computing and Business Information Practice with limited investment on IT infrastructure.
- Many volunteer organizations are moving Not Profit Technologies such as E-Mail, Database and communication support [2, 8].
- Though open standard best Not Profit Technologies gaining popularity but, it has some problem like future services and management or maintenance.
- Cloud computing, in open source platform, is most important and valuable for small organization and NGO sector and even home users.

Conclusion

Technologies are changing. Many organizations and institutions are moving from costly and closed source software and technologies towards open source technology and standards. Developing countries, underdeveloped countries are the main user of Not Profit Technologies [2, 9]. Open stack, delta cloud collaborative, Nuxco, Open ERP, VTiger are some popular name in the field of open cloud computing. A study conducted by Rightscale inc. on 651 companies, out of which [64% of the respondents], 41 % plan to use only open cloud platform; hence this percentage is important as far as current trends towards open source and not profit technology.

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